

Taphofacies and geochemical proxies: tools to analyze paleoclimatic conditions
in the Eocene Naredi Formation, Kutch Basin, India

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Presented by:

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The Kutch Basin

Let's do a routine background check...

Geological Map of the Kutch Basin...

Source: Swarna, K., Biswas, S. K., & Harinarayana, T. (2013).

North Kathiawar Fault

Radhanpur Arch

Composite litholog of the Naredi Formation, Kutch Basin, India

Source: Srivastava et al (2017)

Regressive event
Taphofacies C

Taphofacies C
 Shallow part of the lagoon : Shallowing of the lagoon

Brown Shale. Sporadic Mollusca. Very low diversity. Shells intact. Interlayering of Gypsum. Low energy, tranquil and restricted environment. Shallowing up of the lagoon (Srivastava & Singh, 2017)

LEGEND

- Numulites
- Assilina
- Burrow marks
- Bivalves
- Concretions

Taphofacies B

Green Shale. High amount of Glauconite. Higher hydraulic energy. Moderately low biodiversity. Marginal marine environment. *Nummulites* and fragmented Mollusca. Decrease in the Mollusca : *Nummulites* ratio vertically upwards. *Nummulites* are mostly intact. Haphazard test orientation.

Taphofacies A

Sporadic mollusca in concretions within shale. Sometimes containing glauconite. Intact : Fragmented = 60 : 40. Intact forms found mostly at the centre of the concretions acting as the nucleus. Broken forms found mostly near the periphery. Concretions formed during early stages of diagenesis (Marshall & Pirrie, 2013). Low diversity and restricted environment like that of a lagoon.

Marginal marine environment with rise in the hydraulic energy from bottom to top

Early diagenetic incident in a lagoonal environment

Regressive event

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		Limestone concretion layer with foraminifera on the outer rim Yellow shale, white lime mud vein passing through it, fossils sporadic Green shale with foraminifera and mollusca
		Brown shale with sporadic molluscs and interlayered gypsum
5 m		Grey - brown shale devoid of fossils
		Grey - brown shale has sporadic shells of molluscs
		Green shale with foraminifera and mollusca
		Grey - brown shale with sporadic concretions
		Reddish-brown shale containing small concretions
		Brown shale with burrows and gypsum
0 m		Grey shale with concretions containing bivalve fragments

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Brown shale with gypsum
 Green shale
Electron Image 6

Regressive event

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Taphofacies F

Middle to Inner ramp setting : shallow marginal marine environment

Taphofacies E

Taphofacies D

Brackish water conditions

LEGEND

- Nummulites
- Assilina*
- Burrow marks
- Bivalves
- Concretions

Inner ramp setting : shallow marginal marine environment

Brown shale with sporadic brinaves, glauconite in small pockets, fractures

Assilina dominated in the outer layers of the concretion. *Assilina* concentration decreases towards the centre. Centre of concretions devoid of fossils. Very few *Nummulites* (intact). Fragmentation moderate - <50%

Transportation during formation of the concretions. Ferric core and micritized *Assilina* tests – marginal marine brackish water (Khan et al., 2020).

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(Srivastava & Singh, 2017)

LEGEND

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Facies F

Inner ramp
shallow marginal
environment

Assilina (dominated), few Nummulites, Coral & Ostracods. Corals broken. Intact Nummulites & Ostracods. Fragmentation rate moderate to high, decreasing upwards. Impure limestone. Higher biodiversity compared to the other facies and moderate energy. Shallow marine setting. Middle to Inner ramp setting (Srivastava & Singh, 2017).

Inner ramp setting : shallow marginal marine environment

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Taphofacies F

Middle to Inner ramp setting : shallow marginal marine environment

Assilina dominated, few *Nummulites* and Mollusca. Low to high fragmentation rate increasing upwards. Both sparitized & micritized tests. Patches of completely obliterated tests due to sparitization. Fluctuation in hydraulic energy. Framboidal pyrite. Reducing conditions. Shallow marine setting. Restricted environment. Middle to Inner Ramp (Srivastava & Singh, 2017)

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 (Srivastava & Singh, 2017)

Taphofacies F

Middle to Inner ramp setting : shallow marginal marine environment

Assilina (dominant), few *Nummulites*, Corals, Ostracods, Corals broken

	Green shale
	Brown shale with sporadic bivalves, glauconite in small pockets, fractures with gypsum crystals

Taph

Assilina dominated layers of the...
Assilina concretions towards the center...
 Very few *Num*...
 Fragmentation

Transportation during concretions.
 Ferric core and micritization – marginal marine bra...
 (Khan et al., 2020).

Data Matrix_Naredi

Type of rock	Ch 1	Ch 2	Ch 3	Ch 4	Ch 5	Ch 6	Ch 7	Ch 8	Ch 9	Ch 10	Ch 11	Ch 12	Ch 13	Ch 14	Ch 15	Ch 16	Ch 17	Ch 18	Ch 19	Ch 20	Ch 21	Ch 22	Ch 23	Ch 24	Ch 25	Ch 26	Ch 27	
Con. Sh 1		2	0	2	4	1	0	0	1	1	?	?	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	3	0	1	0	0	2	0	3	0
GS-1 (5)		0	3	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0&1	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
GS-2 (7)		0	3	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0&1	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
Br. Shale 1		2	0	2	4	1	0	0	1	3	?	?	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	0
Con.1 (8)		1	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0&1	0	2	2	0	2	0	0	2	2	1	0	0	0
Imp. Carb 11x		1	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	2	0	1	1&2	0	1&2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Imp. Carb 12		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	2	0	2	1&2	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Assi. Lstone 1 (15)		1	0	1	1	0&1	1	1	0	1&2&3	0	1	0	1	1&2&3	0	2	2&3	0	1	0	0	1&2	1&2	0	2	1	1
Assi. Lstone 2 (16)		1	0	1	1	0&1	1	1	0	1&2	1	1	0	1	1&2	0	2	2&3	0	2	0	0	1&2	1&2	0	2	1	1
Con. Sh 2		2	1	2	4	1	0	0	1	1	?	?	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	3	0	1	0	0	2	0	3	0
Br. Shale 2		2	0	2	4	1	0	0	1	3	?	?	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	0
Br. Shale 3		2	0	2	4	1	0	0	1	3	?	?	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	0
Br. Gp. Shale 1		2	0	2	4	1	0	0	1	3	?	?	0	0	0	3	1	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	0
Br. Gp. Shale 2		2	0	2	4	1	0	0	1	3	?	?	0	0	0	3	1	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	0

27 characters:

They include the fragmentation rate of the different fossils, the assemblage, the type of alteration observed such as micritization, sparitization, etc., changes in vertical and horizontal direction along a particular horizon, the concentration of organisms, the host rock type, etc.

GC values, 100 replicates, cut=1 (tree 0) - Standard Bootstrap

CI - 0.875 | RI - 0.931 | 10,621 trees

Storm event – Harudi
Coquina

Diversity – Based on different Larger benthic foraminifera, Mollusca, and Vertebrate fossils (whole numbers)

Fragmentation – Basically the Fragmentation rate (FR = fragmented bioclast/total bioclast)

Marine: Carbonate Ramp

Marginal Marine: Restricted environment like a lagoon

Tranquil low-energy environment

PCA Analysis on Diversity, Fragmentation rate, Level of concentration of bioclasts and Major fragmentation type

 Marine: Carbonate Ramp Setting

 Storm Deposit – Harudi Coquina Bed

 Marginal Marine: Restricted environment

Naredi Formation

High input of Aluminium – Indicative of contamination

Expected in a marginal marine setting with terrestrial inputs

Low correlation between Al and Ca: They do not get incorporated into the minerals simultaneously

Naredi Formation

Redox proxies:

When the foraminifera bearing horizons are considered they show decrease with increase in the foram concentration

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Some regions show high redox proxies – usually associated with deposition of Pyrite crystals

Pyrite crystals under Scanning Electron Microscope

Naredi Formation

Redox proxies:

These two sets of data do not give a very clear picture. That is why we decided to use a number of different proxies

References:

Wignall and Myers, 1988; Calvert and Pedersen, 1993; Jones and Manning, 1994; Powell et al., 2003; Siebert et al., 2003; Tribovillard et al., 2006; Jiménez-Espejo et al., 2007; Gallego-Torres et al., 2007; 2010; Yilmaz et al., 2010, Reolid and Ruiz, 2012

A black and white photograph of a large, textured rock formation, possibly a fossil or a piece of ancient stone. The rock has a rough, layered appearance with a prominent crack running through it. The lighting is dramatic, highlighting the textures and shadows of the rock.

THANK YOU

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